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Biphyllidae: *Althaesia leri*

Boganiidae: *Helota gemmata*

Boganiidae: *Paracucujus rostratus*

Bothriideridae: *Deretaphrus fossor*

Byturidae: *Byturellus griseus*

Coccinellidae: *Harmonia octomaculata*

Coccinellidae: *Harmonia octomaculata*

DORSAL

VENTRAL

Cucujidae: *Platusus mocrosus*

Endomychidae: *Stenotarsus commodus*

Erotylidae: *Cnecosa inseuta*

Nitidulidae: *Brachypeplus basalis*

Nitidulidae: *Lasioductus marmoratus*

Nitidulidae: *Brachypeplus basalis*

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Cucujidae: *Passandra heros*

Cucujidae: *Passandra heros*

Phloestichidae: *Rhopalobrachium*

Protocucujidae: *Ericmodes*

Aderidae: *Megaxenus papuensis*

Boridae: *Boros unicolor*

Cephaloidea: *Stenotrachelus aeneus*
Tenebrionoidea

MP weak as in
Eucinetoides

Melandryidae: *Eustrophinus*

Melandryidae: *Eustrophinus*

Mycteridae: Genus?

Tenebrionoidea
Oedemeridae: *Calopus angustus*

Prostomidae: *Prostomis*

Tenebrionoidea:
Pyrochroidae: *Cycloderus* sp.

Rhipiphoridae: *Trigonodera schaefferi*

Tenebrionoidea
 Stenotrachelidae: *Stenotrachelus aeneus*

MP weak as in
Eucinetoidae

Tenebrionidae: *Dysantes biluna*

Cerambycidae: *Eurynasa* sp.

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Cerambycidae: *Archetypus frenchi*

Cerambycidae: *Eurynassa* sp.

Cerambycidae: *Eurynassa* sp.

Cerambycidae: *Eurynassa* sp.

Megalopodidae: *Cucujopsis setifer*

Attelabidae: *Merhynchlites wickhami*

Belidae: *Belus* sp.

Brentidae

Ithyceridae: *Ithycerus novoboracensis*

